

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART V. OXIDATION WITH POTASSIUM CHLORATE.

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Bromate, iodate, permanganate and dichromate of potassium were determined potentiometrically, using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. A known weight of each substance was mixed with a known excess of potassium iodide and the required amount of hydrochloric acid to keep its concentration above 5*N*. The excess of potassium iodide was determined by titrating the mixture against standard potassium chlorate. The titrations were conducted at 10° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each case.

In presence of an excess of hydrochloric acid, potassium iodide reacts with chlorate, bromate, iodate, permanganate and dichromate of potassium. The reactions are represented by the equations :—

These reactions have been made use of in the quantitative estimation of bromate, iodate, permanganate and to dichromate of potassium.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

A known weight of each substance was mixed with a known excess of potassium iodide solution and the required amount of hydrochloric acid to keep its concentration above 5*N*. The excess of potassium iodide was determined by titrating the mixture potentiometrically against standard potassium chlorate. The titrations were conducted at 10° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide and a micro-burette was used to add the standard solution near the equivalence point.

The indicator electrode, which consisted of a bright platinum foil, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was coupled with saturated calomel electrode. A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration, as typical of that set, is recorded in the following table

TABLE I.

0.7797 G. of KI and 0.1458 g. of KMnO_4 , dissolved in 20 c. c. of water and 50 c. c. of conc. HCl acid titrated against $M/30\text{-KClO}_3$.

KClO_3	E.M.F.	E/C	KClO_3	E.M.F.	E/C
		(m. volts/c. c.)			(m. volts/c. c.)
0.000 c. c.	0.326 volts		23.500 c. c.	0.628 volts	
0.200	0.336	50	23.700	0.638	50
0.500	0.380	147	23.800	0.646	80
1.000	0.464	168	23.850	0.653	140
2.000	0.492	28	23.875	0.658	200
4.000	0.520	14	23.900	0.664	240
7.000	0.540	7	23.925	0.676	480
10.000	0.556	5	23.950	0.786	4400 (maximum) 1280
13.000	0.564	3	23.975	0.818	320
16.000	0.572	3	24.000	0.826	200
19.000	0.580	3	24.050	0.836	80
22.000	0.590	22	24.150	0.844	40
23.000	0.612	32	24.450	0.856	16
			24.950	0.864	

The titrations, one for each substance, are represented by the curves given in Fig. 1.

DISCUSSION.

For these titrations, with the first few additions of the titrant, the E.M.F. rose abruptly except in a few cases. This was followed by a steady increase in potential till the equivalence point with further additions of the reagent. At the equivalence point, there was a jump in potential in

FIG. 1.

each case. For the addition of 0.025 c. c. of the titrant, the inflection potential was of the order of 70, 125, 110 and 166 m. volts for potassium bromate, potassium iodate, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate. After the equivalence point, there was again a steady rise in the potential on further addition of the reagent.

All these reactions take place in two stages. The two stages of the reaction in the case of potassium iodide and potassium bromate in the presence of a large excess of hydrochloric acid, for example, are as follows:—

and the complete reaction is represented by a single equation as :

In all these titrations, an excess of potassium iodide (according to the complete reaction equation) was added to each of the oxidants, *viz.*,

KBrO_3 , KIO_3 , KMnO_4 and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. This amount of the iodide may or may not be in excess to that required by the oxidant according to the first stage reaction equation.

When the amount of the iodide was in excess to that required by the oxidant, the unreacted iodide was oxidised to iodine on the addition of the titrant (KClO_3).

When all the iodide was oxidised to iodine, the first break in potential was observed.

When the liberated iodine was converted into iodine monochloride on further addition of the titrant,

another break, much larger in magnitude than the first one, took place. This second jump in the E.M.F. corresponded to the equivalence point in the titration.

When the amount of the iodide was not in excess, to that required by the oxidant (considering the first stage reaction equation), the oxidant, left after the oxidation of all the iodide to iodine, reacted with equivalent amount of the liberated iodine to form iodine monochloride. When the unreacted iodine was completely converted into iodine monochloride on the addition of the titrant, a large jump in potential corresponding to the equivalence point took place. In this case, as the iodide was completely oxidised to iodine before the addition of the titrant, only one break in E.M.F. was observed. This corresponded to the equivalence point.

In some titrations, therefore, two breaks in the E.M.F. were noticed, while in others only one was observed depending upon the amount of potassium iodide used in each titration.

From the volume of potassium chlorate corresponding to the equivalence point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. In the following table, the values obtained are compared with the amounts of the substance taken.

TABLE II.

KBrO ₃ taken.	Potassium bromate.		KBrO ₃ found.
	KI added.	KI used for KBrO ₃ .	
0.2516 g.	1.5010 g.	0.7494 g.	0.2513 g.
0.1675	0.8271	0.4990	0.1673
0.1048	0.6176	0.3121	0.1046
0.0673	0.5092	0.2001	0.0671

TABLE II (contd.).

Potassium iodate.

KIO ₃ taken	KI added.	KI used for KIO ₃ .	KIO ₃ found.
0·3210 g.	1·2524 g.	0·4975 g.	0·3206 g.
0·2143	0·8304	0·3322	0·2141
0·1338	0·5133	0·2072	0·1335
0·0856	0·3326	0·1323	0·0853
0·0538	0·2342	0·0832	0·0536

Potassium permanganate.

KMnO ₄ taken.	KI added.	KI used for KMnO ₄ .	KMnO ₄ found.
0·4831 g.	2·0286 g.	1·2682 g.	0·4824 g.
0·1931	0·8371	0·5068	0·1929
0·1458	0·7797	0·3823	0·1456
0·0892	0·4890	0·2339	0·0891
0·0425	0·3318	0·1115	0·0424

Potassium dichromate.

K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ taken.	KI added.	KI used for K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ found.
0·2431 g.	1·9221 g.	1·4107 g.	0·2432 g.
0·1951	0·6798	0·3297	0·1948
0·1446	0·4972	0·2442	0·1443
0·0963	0·4722	0·1623	0·0959
0·0484	0·2823	0·0815	0·0481

These results show that potassium bromate, potassium iodate, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate can be determined by the potentiometric method.

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